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“COOLING MY HEELS”

Love, love, love, love

Love, I am here waiting

No rush, said I.

Wait, wait for your coming.

You're in God's hands.

Though it is not easy

To cool my heels

Cling, cling to Him always

Night and day

Pray to the One above

He holds the master plan

No need to sweat, no need to fret

For, He is love.

The thrill simply inspires me

Minute and hour

Come, come to me gutsy

And kneel, let's kneel.

Please don't you dare lay off.

Stay cool and smile.

Why, why don't you plead

By and by.

The waiting is not in vain

For my Father knows best.

Though it seems long.

But my patience is enough, coz of Your, Lord.